
Final Report

(EU Contract No. SMT4 – CT97 - 7505)

THEMATIC NETWORK ON EUROPEAN STANDARDS FOR METAL INJECTION MOULDING

Working Group 3 - High Strength Materials

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OBJECTIVES

THE OBJECTIVES OF WORKING GROUP 3 WERE THE DEVELOPMENT OF STANDARDS FOR THE FATIGUE AND IMPACT TESTING OF THE CHOSEN MIM MATERIALS. TWO STEELS HAVE BEEN SELECTED AS REPRESENTATIVES OF HEAT TREATABLE HIGH STRENGTH MATERIALS: THE 17-4 PH PRECIPITATION HARDENED STAINLESS STEEL, AND THE LOW ALLOY AISI 4340 STEEL, THE LAST ONE FOR CONVENTIONAL QUENCH AND TEMPER HEAT TREATMENTS.

IT BECAME OBVIOUS AT AN EARLIER STAGE OF THE THEMATIC NETWORK THAT A STANDARD DEFINING BOTH THE FATIGUE AND IMPACT STRENGTH OF MIM MATERIALS WAS OUT OF REACH FOR THE SCOPE OF THE MIM NETWORK. INSTEAD, THE HIGH STRENGTH POTENTIAL OF THESE STEELS AS PRODUCED BY MIM TECHNOLOGY SHOULD BE DEMONSTRATED AND THE RESULTS COULD BE A BASE FOR A MORE EXTENSIVE RESEARCH PROJECT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MIM PRODUCTS FOR HIGH LOADING APPLICATIONS. THE WORK THAT WAS THEN DEVELOPED ONWARD WAS FOCUSING THIS TARGET. MORE DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENTAL WORK AND RESULTS IS MADE ON THE SEVERAL TECHNICAL PROGRESS REPORTS WRITTEN FOR THE SEVERAL WORKSHOPS OF THE MIMNET.

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MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION

MIM MATERIALS THAT ARE SUITABLE FOR HIGH STRENGTH APPLICATIONS ARE LOW ALLOY STEELS AFTER CASE HARDENING OR QUENCH-AND-TEMPER HEAT TREATMENTS, AND 17-4 PH STAINLESS STEEL AFTER HEAT TREATMENT. THE WORK WAS THEN CARRIED OUT ON MIM 17-4 PH AND MIM AISI 4340. RECTANGULAR SHAPE SPECIMENS, 5X10X55 AND 10X10X55 MM³, OF THESE MATERIALS HAVE BEEN SUPPLIED BY PART MANUFACTURERS FOR IMPACT TESTS. DOG-BONE SHAPED SPECIMENS HAVE BEEN SUPPLIED FOR BOTH TENSILE AND FATIGUE TESTS.

FOUR DIFFERENT MIM MANUFACTURERS HAVE SUPPLIED THE SPECIMENS USED IN THE AXIAL FATIGUE WORK AS IT IS SHOWN IN TABLE 1. ALL MATERIALS HAVE BEEN SUPPLIED IN THE AS-SINTERED CONDITION, AS SHOWN IN TABLE 2 (NON-ETCHED CROSS SECTIONS) AND TABLE 3 (ETCHED CROSS SECTIONS). MANUFACTURERS IN ORDER TO PERFORM TENSILE AND IMPACT TESTS DELIVERED A PREVIOUS SET OF SPECIMENS.

TABLE 1 – MATERIALS SUPPLIED FOR TESTS

MATERIAL	CODE	SINT. TEMP. (°C)	ATMOSPHERE	OBS.
17-4 PH	A		VACUUM	φ 3 MM
42CRMO4	B		N ₂	φ 3 MM
17-4 PH	C	1380°C/3H	H ₂	φ 3 MM
17-4 PH	D	1380°C/3H	H ₂	φ 3 MM
42CRMO4	E	1290°C/1H	N ₂	φ 3 MM
17-4 PH	F	1400°C	H ₂	φ 4 MM
17-4 PH	G			φ 3 MM
4340	H			φ 3 MM

TABLE 2 – MATERIALS SUPPLIED FOR TESTS (CROSS SECTIONS)

Material	Picture	Density (g cm ⁻³)	Porosity (%)
A 17-4PH		7.6	4.05
B 42CrMo4		7.38	3.75
C 17-4 PH		7.54	4.05
D 17-4 PH		7.66	2.15

(NON-ETCHED)

TABLE 2 – MATERIALS SUPPLIED FOR TESTS (CROSS SECTIONS) (CONT.)

Material	Picture	Density (g cm ⁻³)	Porosity (%)
<p>E 42CrM04</p>		7.43	4.55
<p>F 17-4 PH</p>		7.60	2.80
<p>G 17-4 PH</p>		7.58	4.15
<p>H 4340</p>		7.51	4.3

(NOT ETCHED)

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Hardness

MACRO AND MICRO HARDNESS TESTS WERE PERFORMED ON AS-SINTERED AND HEAT-TREATED SPECIMENS. LOADS OF 100 G AND 30 KG WERE USED FOR VICKERS MICRO AND MACRO HARDNESS, RESPECTIVELY. THE RESULTS ARE SHOWN IN TABLE 4.

TABLE 4A)- HARDNESS OF MIM MATERIALS SUPPLIED FOR AXIAL FATIGUE TESTS

MATERIAL	CODE	AS-SINTERED				HEAT-TREATED			
		HV0.1	S	HV30	S	HV0.1	S	HV30	S
17-4 PH	A	362	3.3	311	2.8	400	16.1	433	6.4
17-4 PH	C	337	20.4	307	5.1	404	16.4	427	4.4
17-4 PH	D	321	7.1	290	4.3	418	20.8	437	7.3
17-4 PH	F	377	5.7	368	4.7	407	15.4	436	13.9
17-4 PH	G	298	6.2	265	4.1	391	16.0	427	3.9
4340	H	360	21.8	355	11.1	408	25.5	395	15.0

TABLE 4B)- HARDNESS OF MIM MATERIALS SUPPLIED FOR IMPACT, ROTATING AND TENSILE TESTS

MATERIAL	BATCH	HEAT-TREATED	
		HRC	S
MIM17-4 PH	6	42.6	2.3
	9	44.8	1.5
	4	41.6	8.2
	8	40.5	2.3
	5	40.7	2.5
	7	39.1	1.2
	11	40.9	2.8
	13	40.6	3.0
MIM 4340	1	25.7	4.6
	2	29.6	4.9
	12	36.6	8.9
	10	38.6	2.8

Picnometric Density

DENSITY OF THE SPECIMENS HAS BEEN DETERMINED BY GAS (HELIUM) PICNOMETRY, ON THE AS-SINTERED SPECIMENS. THE RESULTS ARE SHOWN IN TABLE 2.

Porosity

IN ORDER TO CHARACTERISE POROSITY, AN OPTICAL MICROSCOPE LINKED TO A COMPUTER IMAGE ANALYSER VIA A VIDEO CAMERA, WAS USED. IMAGE MAGNIFICATION WAS SELECTED ACCORDINGLY TO REPRESENTATIVE AREAS OF POROSITY. TWENTY IMAGES PER SPECIMEN WERE ANALYSED. RESULTS ARE SHOWN IN TABLE 2. AS IT CAN BE SEEN, ALL SPECIMENS SHOW REDUCED OR NO POROSITY BENEATH SURFACE, THE PORES BEING MAINLY ROUND. FOR THE SAME MATERIAL, MAIN DIFFERENCES AMONG DIFFERENT MANUFACTURERS ARE BELIEVED TO BE DUE TO DIFFERENT SINTERING TEMPERATURES. A PLOT OF POROSITY IS SHOWN IN FIGURE 1, AS WELL AS DENSITY, FOR THE SUPPLIED MIM 17-4 PH SPECIMENS.

FIGURE 1 – DENSITY AND POROSITY PLOTS OF THE MIM 17-4 PH MATERIAL

Chemical Analysis

IN ORDER TO CHARACTERISE THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE MIM 17-4PH AND MIM 4340 MATERIALS, SOME ANALYSIS HAVE BEEN DONE ON THE SPECIMENS DELIVERED FOR IMPACT, TENSILE AND ROTATIVE FATIGUE TESTS. MIM 17-4 PH MATERIAL HAS BEEN ANALYSED BY OPTICAL SPECTROSCOPY. HOWEVER, ONE BATCH OF MIM 4340 COULD NOT BE ANALYSED BY THE SPECTROSCOPICAL TECHNIQUE, BECAUSE NO STABLE ARC COULD BE OBTAINED. THIS WAS ATTRIBUTED TO THE HIGH POROSITY OF THE SAMPLES. ONLY CARBON CONTENT WAS DETERMINED. AS IT CAN BE SEEN, ONE MIM 4340 BATCH SHOWS A VERY LOW CARBON CONTENT. RESULTS OF THESE ANALYSES ARE SHOWN IN TABLE 5.

TABLE 5 – CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF MIM MATERIALS

MATERIAL		C	SI	Mn	P	S	Cr	Cu	Ni	Nb	Mo
17-4 PH	NOMINAL	<0.07	<1.0	<1.0	<0.04	<0.03	15.5-17.5	3.0-5.0	3.0-5.0	0.15-0.45	-
	BATCH 4	0.04	0.41	0.11	0.02	0.003	17	4.74	4.17	0.32	-
	BATCH 5	<0.01	0.38	0.08	0.01	0.01	16.2	3.52	3.94	0.31	-
	BATCH 6	<0.01	0.39	0.45	0.02	0.002	16.5	4.31	3.41	0.28	-
4340	NOMINAL	0.38-0.43	0.20-0.35	0.60-0.80	-	-	0.70-0.90	-	1.65-2.00	-	0.20-0.30
	BATCH 1	0.17	NOT ANALYSED								
	BATCH 2	0.44									
	BATCH 3	0.45									

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HEAT TREATMENT

THE HEAT TREATMENT USED FOR BOTH MATERIALS, I.E. MIM 17-4PH AND MIM 4340, WAS CHOSEN IN ORDER TO HAVE A COMPROMISE BETWEEN STRENGTH AND HARDNESS, AND WAS AGREED WITHIN WG 3 MEMBERS, AS FOLLOWS:

MIM 17-4 PH

SOLUTION TREATMENT: 1H/ 1050°C - AGEING: 4H/ 480°C

MIM 4340

NORMALISING: 20 MIN / 870°C - HARDENING: 15 MIN / 840°C - TEMPERING: 2H / 425°C

THE SPECIMENS USED FOR TENSILE, IMPACT AND ROTATIVE FATIGUE TESTS HAVE BEEN HEAT TREATED IN NITROGEN (MIM 17-4 PH) AND SALT BATH, AIR AND OIL (MIM 4340). ALL THE ONES USED FOR AXIAL FATIGUE HAVE BEEN HEAT TREATED IN VACUUM AND COOLED IN NITROGEN. THE HARDNESS UPON HEAT TREATMENT WAS IN THE DESIRED RANGE. HEAT TREATED MICROSTRUCTURES ARE SHOWN IN TABLE 6.

TABLE 6 – HEAT TREATED MICROSTRUCTURES (ETCHED) OF THE MIM MATERIALS

MATERIAL		MATERIAL	
A MIM 17-4 PH			
C MIM 17-4 PH			
D MIM 17-4 PH			

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MECHANICAL TESTS

Tensile Tests

THE TENSILE SPECIMENS TESTED IN TENSION SHOWED SOMEWHAT SCATTERING VALUES, REGARDING BOTH THE TENSILE STRENGTH AND ELONGATION. ALTHOUGH THE YIELD AND TENSILE STRENGTH ARE COMPARABLE TO THOSE OF BULK MATERIAL, THE DUCTILITY IS ABOUT FIVE TIMES LOWER. THESE EFFECTS WERE BELIEVED TO BE DUE TO HIGH POROSITY AND SUB SURFACE CRACKS OBSERVED IN SOME SPECIMENS. RESULTS OF THE TENSILE TESTS ARE SHOWN IN TABLE 7.

TABLE 7 - RESULTS OF TENSILE TESTS

MATERIAL	BATCH	0.2% YIELD STRENGTH (MPa)	TENSILE STRENGTH (MPa)	ELONGATION (%)
MIM 17-4 PH	4	-	842	0.2
	5	1088	1209	4.1
	6	1134	1235	6.2
	13	1153	1255	5.2
MIM 4340	1	775	796	0.8
	12	1207	1375	3.3

Impact Tests

TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE DESIRED NEAR FULL DENSITY THAT CAN BE ACHIEVED BY MIM IT WAS DECIDED WITHIN WG3 THAT THE SPECIMENS TO BE TESTED WOULD HAVE A NOTCH. THE NOTCH WAS MACHINED TO A DEPTH OF 20% OF THE THICKNESS, AFTER HEAT TREATMENT.

THE ENERGY VALUES FOUND FOR THE TESTED SPECIMENS WERE ABOUT TEN TIMES LOWER WHEN COMPARED TO THE BULK MATERIAL FOR THE SAME HEAT TREATMENT. AS ALL THE SPECIMENS SHOWED MODERATE TO HIGH POROSITY, AND SINCE PORES ACT AS CRACK NUCLEATION SITES, IT WAS BELIEVED THAT POROSITY REDUCED SERIOUSLY THE REQUIRED BREAKING ENERGY. HENCE, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE EFFECT OF POROSITY THAT IS MORE PRONOUNCED IN IMPACT TESTS BECAUSE OF THE MUCH HIGHER STRAIN RATE, LOW IMPACT ENERGY COULD BE EXPECTED. TABLE 8 SHOWS RESULTS OF THE PERFORMED IMPACT TESTS.

TABLE 8 – IMPACT TESTS (AVERAGE RESULTS)

MATERIAL	FRACTURE SURFACE	CODE	NOMINAL DIMENSIONS (W x D x L) mm ³	ENERGY (J cm ²)	HARDNESS HRC
MIM 17-4 PH		8	9 x 9 x 52	7.46	40.5
MIM 17-4 PH		7	5 x 10 x 54	3.17	27.9
MIM 4340		2	9 x 9 x 52	2.6	39.1

Fatigue Tests

Rotating Fatigue

CONCERNING THE MIM 17-4 PH MATERIAL, IT WAS FOUND THAT ALL THE SPECIMENS FALL IN THE SAME SCATTER BAND. HOWEVER THIS SCATTER BAND IS CONSIDERABLE LOWER THAN ONE SET OF DATA FOUND IN LITERATURE FOR REVERSED BENDING TESTS, DESPITE THE FACT THAT NOT ENOUGH INFORMATION IS GIVEN IN THE MENTIONED LITERATURE TO EXPLAIN THIS DIFFERENCE. THE ROTATING FATIGUE TESTS PERFORMED ON THE MIM 4340 MATERIAL WERE NOT ENOUGH TO ALLOW AN ESTIMATION OF THE MATERIAL BEHAVIOUR. THOUGH NO LITERATURE DATA FROM MIM SPECIMENS HAVE BEEN FOUND FOR COMPARISON, THE AVAILABLE RESULTS SEEM TO BE SOMEWHAT LOW.

FOR BOTH MATERIALS, THE FACTORS FOUND TO AFFECT THE TEST RESULTS WERE:

- SURFACE CONDITION: ROUGHNESS, OXIDATION AND/OR REACTION LAYERS
- POROSITY
- EFFECT OF MOULD SEPARATION LINE LOCATION, AS MOST OF THE FRACTURES ORIGINATED ALONG THIS LINE, MORE EXACTLY ON NOTCHES, SMALL CRACKS AND SUB SURFACE HOLES.

FIGURE 2 AND FIGURE 3 SHOW THE ROTATING FATIGUE PLOTS OF THE MIM 17-4 PH AND MIM 4340 MATERIAL, RESPECTIVELY, AS WELL AS THE ESTIMATED FATIGUE LIMIT (EFL) FOR MIM 17-4 PH.

FIGURE 2 - ROTATING FATIGUE PLOTS OF THE MIM 17-4 PH

FIGURE 3 - ROTATING FATIGUE PLOTS OF THE MIM 4340

Axial Fatigue

AXIAL FATIGUE TESTS PERFORMED ON THE MIM 17-4 PH MATERIAL SHOWED STRESS LEVELS SLIGHTLY ABOVE THE ONES OBTAINED FOR THE ROTATING TESTS. THOUGH BELONGING TO DIFFERENT BATCHES (FROM THE SAME MANUFACTURERS), THE TESTED SPECIMENS ALSO SHOWED THE SAME DEFECTS AS THE ONES FOUND IN THE SPECIMENS USED IN THE ROTATING FATIGUE TESTS. RESULTS ARE SHOWN IN FIGURE 4.

CONCERNING THE MIM 4340 MATERIAL, FIGURE 5, THE AXIAL FATIGUE RESULTS WERE DISTINCT, WHEN COMPARED TO THE STRESS LEVELS OBTAINED FOR THE ROTATING FATIGUE: THE STRESS WAS ABOUT TWICE WHEN COMPARED TO THIS LAST ONE. THE MIM 4340 SPECIMENS SHOWED PARTICULAR GOOD SURFACE QUALITY, WHERE VERY LITTLE PORES AT THE SURFACE OR UNDERNEATH HAVE BEEN OBSERVED, ALTHOUGH HAVING A TOTAL POROSITY OF ABOUT 4%. FROM LITERATURE, FOR A WROUGHT SAE 4340 MATERIAL, SIMILAR HEAT TREATMENT AND TESTED BY PLANE BENDING, FATIGUE STRENGTH AT 10^6 OF ABOUT 600 MPa WAS REPORTED. THE RESULTS OBTAINED FOR THE MIM 4340 MATERIAL ARE VERY CLOSE TO THIS WROUGHT MATERIAL, WHICH IS INDICATIVE OF THE PROMISING FATIGUE STRENGTH OF THE MIM MATERIAL, IF PARTICULAR CARE IS TAKEN ON THE PREPARATION OF MIM PARTS.

FIGURE 4 - AXIAL FATIGUE PLOTS OF THE MIM 17-4 PH MATERIAL FROM DIFFERENT MANUFACTURERS

FIGURE 5 – AXIAL FATIGUE PLOTS OF THE MIM 4340 MATERIAL (RED DOT SHOWS WROUGHT MATERIAL VALUE FROM LITERATURE).

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CONCLUSIONS

TAKING INTO ACCOUNT ALL THE WORK PERFORMED ALONG THE MIMNET, AND REPORTED ON THE SEVERAL PROGRESS REPORTS, ONE CAN CONCLUDE THAT:

- The tensile strength properties are within the range that can be expected for the performed heat treatments, taking into account that the materials are made by PM. The MIM 17-4 PH values are well above the MPIF "typical" values which are however for an unspecified heat treatment.
- The tensile ductility is low as can be expected for porous materials. MIM 17-4 PH is close to the "typical" MPIF value.
- The hardness values are in the desired range but differ somewhat between manufacturers.
- The impact values are about one order of magnitude below the values for dense material with the same heat treatment. This is not unexpected taking into account the porosity of MIM materials. A similar effect was indeed shown by the tensile ductility.
- New impact tests have been suggested using non-notched specimens and better quality specimens.
- It has been shown that when surface quality was improved, MIM materials can show fatigue properties comparable to traditional wrought materials, making them suitable for high loading purposes. So, particular attention is recommended on mould preparation, e.g. partition lines (as the majority of failures occurred along this line), in order to allow appropriate properties.

KNOWING THAT FATIGUE PROPERTIES ARE OF GREAT IMPORTANCE IN PART AUTOMATIC DESIGN, A MORE EXTENSIVE PROGRAM IS NEEDED AIMING TO OBTAIN A MORE COMPLETE DATA BASE ON MIM MATERIALS. AS SUCH RESEARCH IS HIGHLY COSTLY, A EUROPEAN COOPERATIVE RESEARCH PROGRAM SHOULD BE THE BEST SOLUTION.

Note: An extensive fatigue-testing programme was proposed to the MIMNet partners, in order to achieve a more complete as possible set of results. However, due to lack of funding this programme was not possible to perform.